

THE MAIN METHODS OF ANALYSIS OF WRITTEN AND SPOKEN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Many differences between written English and spoken English can be clearly distinguished, as there are many elements in which a clear contrast can be observed. Written English is the English that is referred to in texts and other similar material. Spoken language is what a person hears and uses to communicate with others. While both written and spoken language can be used as a means of communication, the key difference between written and spoken English is that written English is text-based and spoken English is not. In this article, let's look at the differences between these two types with some examples.

In our country, it has long been believed that learning English is necessary. But can you apply what you learned in school to everyday life? This question often deprives you of motivation in learning English, therefore it is best to make a decision on learning a foreign language when you have set a specific goal for yourself and already know where and how you will apply the acquired knowledge.

Knowledge of spoken English is becoming more and more in demand

It is important to decide which type of speech should be emphasized: oral or written. Spoken English is becoming very important today. Many organizations have long been recruiting employees with a basic knowledge of the spoken language: this makes it possible to negotiate with foreign partners. Yes, and learning to speak

it is much easier, because for this you no longer need to sit at the table with a book: now almost everyone has the opportunity to learn English online using a computer and the Internet. You can always take such a lesson with you anywhere by recording it on your mobile device. The success of language learning lies in the systematic study of it. It is important to listen to English every day, using every free minute for this, recording dialogues, audio books and even songs will help you with this. All you need is headphones and a player, and a fresh lesson is always at hand. Lessons of this format will come in handy even if we are learning English from scratch. It is best to use ready-made programs, the lessons in which are built in ascending order of level. The technique from the English Club TV channel is very well thought out: in these

video clips, the developers take into account both age and level of knowledge.

Written English is also very important.

You can learn English online and with such a bias, and quite successfully. Do not underestimate the importance of the ability to express your thoughts in writing: these skills will also come in handy, and not only in everyday life, but also in professional activities. Knowing English, you will be able to translate, for example, instructions for a foreign product or visit a foreign Internet site, correspond with foreign friends or business partners.

Written English is much more difficult than spoken English, in fact, it is much more difficult than any other language. The difficulty is not in grammar, but in the rules of writing themselves. Most of the words do not agree with any rules at all, so you just have to memorize them. But all this is compensated by the easily accessible structure of the grammar. Therefore, starting to learn English from scratch, you need to aim yourself at the fact that it is important to master both written and oral forms. It is enough to regularly devote time to classes and choose the way of studying that is convenient for yourself. It is also important to repeat the material covered and constantly test yourself. When comparing English in terms of speaking or writing, it should be remembered that in writing, sentences can be planned in advance and rechecked, so the writer has time to create more complex structures. Spoken utterances are usually simpler and shorter. Subjects, in particular, tend to be shorter in spoken language than in written language.

A typical written statement would look like this:

The group of young people (that's all subject) who were sitting at the next table were making so much noise that my friends and I found it difficult to continue our conversation.

In oral speech, this statement could look like this:

There were a lot of young people at the next table. They were making so much noise, we couldn't talk.

Written language mostly consists of complete sentences, while in conversation complete sentences are often unnecessary.

- When are you seeing her?

- Half past eight?

- At your place?

- No, at Andy's.

Oral utterances are often composed more freely, "loosely" than written utterances.

Last Wednesday it was, I was just going to work...

This guy who ranks up, he's an architect...

Here, additional information is supplied not through subordinate clauses and not in a separate sentence.

Also, 'fronting' is characteristic of oral speech, when another member of the sentence, and not the subject, may come first.

People like that I just can't stand!

Strange people they are!

For written speech, this feature is not typical.

When we talk about the differences between written and oral speech, we must remember that oral speech is often informal, and written, on the contrary, is formal. Therefore, oral speech is often characterized by the same features that are characteristic of informal English. Written language often uses longer, less common vocabulary, with more synonyms, which is typical of the formal style. In spoken language, people often prefer shorter and more general words and expressions. Also, the repetition of the same words is often used. Another distinctive feature of oral speech is the use of phrasal verbs, while in written speech, they are replaced by formal non-phrasal verbs.

The peculiarity of written English is that it allows us to organize our ideas and create texts. You will notice that when you read an article or news item, it is very well organized. It follows a certain structure.

This organizational factor does not appear in spoken English. Also written English, since it is often a text that has a direct linguistic flow. It is true that there are pauses to convey a clear idea, but it is fluid. This gives us an idea of written English. Now let's turn our attention to spoken English. Also, unlike written English, in spoken English we can detect differences in the manner of speaking. For example, people in different contexts have different accents. The way an American speaks may be different from a Canadian or a British one. Another difference is that spoken English has utterances. They refer to the pauses between speeches. They cannot be seen in writing. The case of the language or the formality of the language also differ in spoken English. It can be more informal than written English, although there are exceptions.

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